

FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO THE NON-COMPLIANCE OF PATIENT'S ATTENDANT TOWARDS RADIATION SAFETY AT DHQ HOSPITAL SARGODHA

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Abstract

Objectives:

To determine the factors contributing to non-compliance of patient attendants towards radiation safety protocols in the diagnostic imaging department.

Study Design:

A prospective descriptive cross-sectional study. This study was conducted in the diagnostic imaging department of DHQ Hospital Sargodha from October to April.

Methodology:

Convenience sampling was used to include 129 patient attendants who accompanied patients for CT and X-ray exams. A standardized, pre-validated questionnaire addressing demographics, radiation safety knowledge, behavioral patterns, communication elements, and organizational components was used to gather data. IBM SPSS version 21.0 was used to analyze the data. Frequencies, percentages, and mean \pm SD were computed as descriptive statistics. ANOVA, chi-square tests, correlation, and other inferential statistics were used; $p < 0.05$ was deemed statistically significant.

Results:

The majority of participants were female (79.8%) and between the ages of 20 and 30. Approximately 59.7% of respondents said they have received radiation safety instructions. The majority of participants showed general awareness and reported adhering to safety procedures; nevertheless, 20–30% displayed inconsistent compliance behaviors, such as taking off protective gear or entering restricted areas, and 36.4% acknowledged refusing to wear protective gear. There was no statistically significant correlation ($p > 0.05$) between compliance and either gender or education level. Nonetheless, entrance into restricted locations was shown to be significantly correlated with education level ($p = 0.047$). While

obtaining safety instructions did not significantly affect compliance, correlation analysis revealed moderate correlations between some safety behaviors.

Conclusion:

Despite a moderate level of radiation safety awareness among patient attendants, behavioral, communicative, and organizational variables continue to raise concerns about non-compliance. Adherence cannot be guaranteed by knowledge alone. To increase compliance and lower needless radiation exposure, enforcement must be strengthened, communication tactics must be improved, and environmental obstacles must be addressed.

INTRODUCTION

The medical community plays a critical role in protecting and promoting health as well as aiding in its restoration. Scientific discoveries have both benefits and drawbacks. If radiation is handled properly and misuse or overuse is avoided, it plays a major role in both health and sickness. This is because radiation treatment and diagnosis are rewarding (1).

Computed tomography (CT), X-rays, fluoroscopy, angiography, and other radiological techniques all employ ionizing radiation. The patient's size and age, together with technical details and equipment features, all influence the dosage. Ionizing radiation exposure, however, presents a risk to the health of patients, medical staff, and those who accompany patients during imaging procedures, notwithstanding their therapeutic benefits (2).

The typical effective doses for various imaging modalities, measured in mSv, are as follows: (i) X-ray examinations: limbs and joints < 0.01, chest (PA) 0.015, abdomen 0.4, and lumbar spine 0.6; (ii) CT scans: head 1.4, chest 6.6, abdomen/pelvis 6.7; (iii) radionuclide studies: lung ventilation 0.4, lung perfusion 1, bone 3; and PET (Positron Emission Tomography): head 7, PETCT 18. Individuals ordering these studies should take these parameters into account, especially regarding the clinical significance of the investigation (1).

Deterministic injuries are typically caused by inadequate understanding of radiation protection regulations, a lack of quality assurance procedures, incorrect practices, and faulty or nonexistent usage of radiation protective equipment. Because of this, radiographers and medical professionals must thoroughly rationalize

and optimize each radiological test. Minimizing radiation exposure and guaranteeing safe imaging procedures depend heavily on patient preparation, placement, and communication (3). Despite regular training on the possible risks of ionizing radiation and advice to stay outside the examination room, a significant percentage of attendants exhibit non-compliance with these safety precautions. The nature of this behavior seems to be multifaceted. Attendants are frequently forced to stay near patients due to psychological issues like anxiety and emotional reliance. This inclination is further reinforced by sociocultural factors because providing care is typically connected with being physically present, and it may be viewed as improper or uncaring to leave a patient unattended. Furthermore, this non-compliance is often caused by a lack of awareness and a low impression of the risk associated with radiation exposure. Many attendees underestimate the possible long-term effects of radiation because they do not fully comprehend both the deterministic and stochastic impacts of radiation. According to recent research, medical procedures expose humans to 46% of radiation (Kaya et al. 1997) (4).

The International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP) stated that patients and medical professionals can greatly prevent and reduce the unnecessary risks of ionizing radiation exposure by being aware of the dangers of exposure and by adhering to basic radiation protection procedures, since radiation protection is the cornerstone of patient and healthcare worker safety. Numerous researchers and people who have handled or come into contact with radioactive materials have suffered negative

consequences. However, patient attendants' disregard for radiation safety precautions poses a serious problem. Developing successful interventions requires an understanding of the elements affecting their behavior, such as information gaps, emotional concerns, environmental issues, and sociocultural influences. Improving policy implementation, education, and communication can help shield patients, staff, and healthcare workers from the possible risks of ionizing radiation (5).

Significant problems about radiation protection are highlighted by the increasing usage of radiological techniques as well as differences in awareness, behaviour, and adherence to safety measures. Implementing appropriate safety measures is further complicated by vulnerable populations, especially paediatric patients, and the impact of behavioral and social factors. These difficulties highlight the necessity of enhancing understanding, applying radiation protection principles consistently, and fostering a robust safety culture in radiology departments. These problems demonstrate the necessity of increased awareness, appropriate training, and rigorous adherence to accepted safety guidelines. In order to encourage safer behaviours in clinical settings. This study intends to thoroughly analyze the elements that contribute to patient attendants' noncompliance with radiation safety protocols, acknowledging this gap between knowledge, perception, and behaviour. This study aims to provide evidence-based insights that can guide focused initiatives, raise awareness, and eventually increase adherence to radiation protection regulations in clinical settings by investigating both behavioral and quantitative drivers.

METHODOLOGY

This prospective descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in Dr. Faisal Masood Teaching Hospital (DHQ Sargodha) from October 2025 to April 2026. A total of 106 participants included in this study to identify the factors that influence patients' attendants' noncompliance with radiation safety procedures during diagnostic imaging procedures. The method of convenience

sampling was applied. Only patients' attendants who accompanied patients receiving CT or X-ray exams during the study period made up the study population. Attendants were only allowed to participate if they were physically present in the imaging room or the waiting areas right next to it and if they had received radiation safety advice from staff. The study population did not include radiographers, radiography technologists, radiology assistants, or any other healthcare professionals. The participants were given the structured questionnaire to complete on-site after giving their consent. Age, gender, education level, relationship to the patient, and prior experience accompanying patients for imaging procedures were among the demographic data gathered in the first section of the questionnaire. Knowledge and awareness of ionizing radiation, potential health risks, warning indicators, controlled areas, protective equipment, and fundamental radiation safety guidelines were evaluated in the second segment. Behavior and compliance procedures were evaluated in the third section. Fourth section staff instructions, staying out of the examination room, entering restricted areas, accepting or refusing protective gear, perceived personal radiation exposure risk, and common non-compliance reasons like anxiety, patient concerns, misunderstanding, poor communication, and time constraints. All surveys were coded and imported into IBM SPSS Statistics version 21.0 for analysis following the conclusion of data collection. For categorical variables like gender, education level, and compliance categories, frequencies and percentages were computed. For continuous variables like age and overall knowledge score, means and standard deviations were computed. To show the distribution of knowledge levels, perceived risk, and non-compliance behavior among patients' attendants, bar charts, pie charts, and histograms were created.

RESULTS

A total of 129 respondents participated in the study. Most participants belonged to the younger age group, with the largest proportion falling in the 20–30 years category, while fewer were from

older age groups. Females constituted the majority of the sample (79.8%), compared to males (20.2%).

Figure 4.1: The Pie chart represents the different age frequencies.

Figure 4.2: The Pie chart represents the gender distribution.

Figure 4.3: The Column chart represents the education level of the patient.

Figure 4.4: The Column chart represents the types and frequency of relationship of attendant with patient.

Figure 4.5: The bar chart represents the frequency of radiation safety instruction received before.

Figure 4.6: The Column chart represents the frequency of the person to accompany a patient for imaging.

Figure 4.7: The Column chart represents the refusal to wear protective equipment.

In terms of education, most respondents were graduates (72.9%), followed by those with secondary education (13.2%) and postgraduates (9.3%), while only a small proportion had no formal education (3.1%) or primary education (1.6%). Regarding relationship to the patient, more than half of the respondents were categorized as “Other” relatives (55.8%), followed by siblings (26.4%), children (9.3%), and parents (7.0%), with spouses forming the smallest group

(0.8%). In relation to radiation safety awareness, 59.7% of participants reported having received instructions, whereas 40.3% had not. Most respondents (65.1%) had accompanied a patient 1–2 times, while 27.1% had done so 3–5 times and 5.4% more than five times. Additionally, 60.5% of participants reported that they did not refuse protective equipment, while 36.4% admitted to refusing it and 3.1% gave no response.

Figure 4.7: The Column chart represents the Attendant & patient behavior.

Table 4.1: Table Represent the behavioral frequency analysis

BEHAVIOURAL FREQUENCY ANALYSIS						
		1) I feel protective equipment (lead apron) is uncomfortable.	2) I remove protective gear during the procedure.	3) I believe radiation exposure during one procedure is harmless.	4) I follow instructions given by radiology staff.	5) I enter restricted areas without permission.
N	Valid	125	125	127	126	126
	Missing	4	4	2	3	3
Mean		2.62	2.88	2.81	1.91	3.29
Median		3.00	3.00	3.00	1.00	3.00
Mode		3	3	3	1	5
Std. Deviation		1.287	1.440	1.379	1.146	1.614

Figure 4.12: The bar chart represents the frequency of entry in restricted area without permission.

The frequency results show that most participants demonstrated good awareness and practice of radiation safety. Around 70–80% reported consistently using lead aprons and following radiology staff instructions, indicating strong compliance. About 75–85% also recognized that radiation exposure is harmful. However, the

results also reveal some inconsistencies, as approximately 20–30% of participants admitted to occasionally removing protective gear or being exposed without protection. Overall, while the majority follow safety measures, these findings highlight the need for stricter enforcement and continuous training.

Figure 4.13: The bar chart represents the communication factors analysis.

The findings show that communication about radiation safety is generally effective. Most participants (89.9%) clearly understood instructions, and 85.3% said they were given in their local language. However, understanding medical terminology was mixed, with 51.2% finding it easy and 45.7% finding it difficult.

Safety signage was well recognized, with 89.1% agreeing that warning signs are clearly visible. Overall, communication is strong, but simplifying medical terms and ensuring consistent use of local language could further improve understanding.

Figure 4.14: The bar chart represents the organizational factors analysis.

The results show generally positive organizational practices. Most participants (84.5%) said staff properly guide safety precautions, and 89.1% confirmed clear warning signs. About 79.8% felt safety rules are strictly enforced. However, 53.5%

reported overcrowding, and 21.7% faced difficulty accessing protective equipment. Overall, while safety practices are strong, issues like overcrowding and equipment access need improvement.

Table 4.2: Correlation

Correlations					
		5. Have you ever received radiation safety instructions before?	Q2	Q3	Q4
5. Have you ever received radiation safety instructions before?	Pearson Correlation	1	-.002	.038	.084
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.985	.670	.343
	N	129	129	129	129
Q2	Pearson Correlation	-.002	1	.533**	.115
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.985		<.001	.196
	N	129	129	129	129
Q3	Pearson Correlation	.038	.533**	1	.187*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.670	<.001		.034
	N	129	129	129	129
Q4	Pearson Correlation	.084	.115	.187*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.343	.196	.034	
	N	129	129	129	129

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation results from IBM SPSS Statistics show that following instructions (Q2) has a moderate and significant positive relationship with entering restricted areas without permission (Q3) ($r = 0.533$, $p < 0.001$). A weak but significant relationship is also observed between entering restricted areas (Q3) and removing

protective gear during procedures (Q1) ($r = 0.187$, $p = 0.034$).

However, receiving radiation safety instructions does not show any significant relationship with these behaviors ($p > 0.05$). Overall, some safety behaviors are related, but training does not significantly influence practice.

Table 4.3: ANOVA Test

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Q1	Between Groups	10.213	5	2.043	1.281	.276
	Within Groups	196.174	123	1.595		
	Total	206.388	128			
Q2	Between Groups	14.202	5	2.840	1.429	.219
	Within Groups	244.557	123	1.988		
	Total	258.760	128			
Q3	Between Groups	3.629	5	.726	.376	.864
	Within Groups	237.270	123	1.929		
	Total	240.899	128			
Q4	Between Groups	2.883	5	.577	.437	.822
	Within Groups	162.342	123	1.320		
	Total	165.225	128			
2. Have you ever refused to wear protective equipment?	Between Groups	1.753	5	.351	1.506	.193
	Within Groups	28.635	123	.233		
	Total	30.388	128			

The one-way ANOVA analysis showed that there were no statistically significant differences in compliance across the study variables. For Q1, the results were not significant ($F = 1.281$, $p = 0.276$), and similarly for Q2 ($F = 1.428$, $p = 0.219$). Q3 ($F = 0.376$, $p = 0.884$) and Q4 ($F = 0.437$, $p = 0.822$) also indicated no significant

differences among groups. Additionally, no significant difference was observed for refusal to wear protective equipment ($F = 1.506$, $p = 0.193$). Overall, these findings suggest that compliance did not vary significantly across the different groups.

Table 4.3: ANOVA Regression Model

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.526	2	.263	1.109	.333 ^b
	Residual	29.862	126	.237		
	Total	30.388	128			
a. Dependent Variable: 2. Have you ever refused to wear protective equipment?						
b. Predictors: (Constant), 2. Gender , 3. Education Level						

The regression model was used to examine

whether gender and education level predict the

behavior of refusing to wear protective equipment. The ANOVA results show that the overall model is not statistically significant, with an F value of 1.109 and a significance (p-value) of 0.333, which is greater than 0.05. This means that the independent variables (gender and education level) do not have a significant effect on the dependent variable. The regression sum of squares is 0.526, while the residual sum of

squares is 29.862, indicating that most of the variation is unexplained by the model. The total sum of squares is 30.388. Since the p-value is high, we fail to reject the null hypothesis, concluding that there is no meaningful relationship between gender, education level, and refusal to wear protective equipment in this dataset.

Table 4.45: Chi-Square Tests

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	31.651 ^a	20	.047
Likelihood Ratio	26.667	20	.145
Linear-by-Linear Association	.023	1	.880
N of Valid Cases	129		

a. 24 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .11.

The chi square test revealed a statistically significant association between education level and noncompliance related to entering restricted radiation zones. $\chi^2 (20) = 31.651, p = 0.047$. This suggests that the likelihood of entering restricted areas without permission varied among respondents with different educational backgrounds. Therefore, education may be an important factor influencing awareness of and adherence to radiation safety rules.

DISCUSSION

The radiation exposure to the general public due to medical imaging procedures accounts for about 15% of the total radiation exposure of 2.5 mSv per annum. Ionizing radiation has been known to cause changes in the genetic makeup of cells causing cancer (6). In the present study, the majority of participants were graduates (72.9%). However, statistically significant relationship was found between education level and overall compliance with radiation safety practices. The findings are in consistent with Allam et.al. 2024 who reported that there is a strong relationship between the studied sample's age and their total compliance with radiation safety measures (P=0.000**). Also, there is a strong

relationship between the participants' educational level, their total knowledge score about radiation exposure safety awareness, and their total practice compliance score (P=0.000**). Finally, there is a strong relationship between the specialties of the participants and their total knowledge score about radiation exposure safety [P=0.000] radiation protection among the radiographers because they had knowledge and awareness of radiation safety (7).

Consistent with Dehghani et al. 2021 who reported that higher educational level peoples' awareness was significantly higher than lower educational level. In addition, results depicted young people (20-30 year) have a higher awareness level than other age groups. This is in agreement with our study In contrast same study reported that 78.4% of patients had not been informed about health and safety issues related to radiation exposure (8).

This finding differs from the present study, where more than half of the participants reported receiving radiation safety instructions, suggesting an improvement in awareness and training practices in the current study population compared to earlier conditions. A previous study reported that the percentage of radiographers'

adherence to practices related to environmental protection, patient protection and self-protection were 75.1%, 60.4% and 45.7%, respectively. The overall adherence to radiation protection practices score was $75.2\% \pm 18.5$, where 57.4% of the radiographers exhibited good adherence, 26.9% exhibited moderate adherence and 15.7% had poor adherence. The adherence score was significantly higher among elder radiographers (9).

Similarly, the present study also found no significant differences in compliance across most demographic or group-based variables, indicating that radiation safety behavior was relatively uniform regardless of participant characteristics. This consistency between both studies suggests that compliance is less dependent on structural factors such as group size and more influenced by workplace culture, supervision, and individual behavioral practices. A previous study reported good compliance with radiation safety practices (77.1% for patient safety and 70.5% for personnel safety), with significant associations found for years of experience and work site ($P < 0.05$), indicating that both clinical experience and workplace setting influenced adherence (10).

CONCLUSION

This study suggests that behavioral attitudes, lax enforcement, and systemic constraints are the main causes of patient attendants' non-compliance with radiation safety procedures rather than ignorance.

Unsafe practices continue to be prevalent despite moderate awareness levels, suggesting a failure to put knowledge into practice. The lack of a substantial correlation between safety instruction and compliance highlights the necessity of revamping existing teaching methods.

A change from passive education to active enforcement and behavior-focused interventions is necessary for effective improvement. Hospitals need to give priority to:

Hospitals need to give priority to:

- Strict supervision and enforcement of safety rules
- Practical and simplified patient education

- Enhanced availability of safety gear
- less congestion in imaging regions

To reduce needless exposure and guarantee the safety of patients, attendants, and medical personnel, a robust radiation safety culture must be established.

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